

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

Welcome to the seventh issue in 2022. I am very pleased to announce the journal's improved Scopus CiteScore of 2.7 and the Web of Science impact factor of 1.056 for 2021, indicating another scientifically successful year. On behalf of the J.UCS team, I would like to thank all the authors for their sound research contributions, the reviewers for their very helpful suggestions, and the consortium members for their financial support. Your commitment and dedicated work have contributed significantly to the long-lasting success of our journal.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce four accepted papers from four different countries and 11 involved authors.

Daisy Ferreira Brito, Monalessa P. Barcellos and Gleison Santos from Brazil address in their research a pattern language to support software measurement planning for statistical process control. More specifically, they use the Goal-Question-Metric format and organize it in a Measurement Planning Pattern Language. Ajay Kumar from India presents a hybridized neuro-fuzzy approach for software reliability prediction and validates the proposed approach by applying the neuro-fuzzy method to a software failure dataset. Jesus Serrano-Guerrero, Bashar Alshouha, Francisco P. Romero and Jose A. Olivas from Spain conduct a comparative study of affective knowledge-enhanced emotion detection in Arabic language. Jing Qiu, Feng Dong and Guanglu Sun from China propose and discuss a disassembly method based on a code extension selection network by combining traditional linear sweep and recursive traversal methods.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

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